
CORPORATE GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

Corporate governance is a crucial concept that encompasses procedures, traditions, regulations, and institutions that guide organizations and businesses in their actions, management, and oversight of their activities. It is essential for creating an optimal investment climate, enabling competitive firms to have a robust foothold in efficient financial markets. Effective corporate governance is crucial for countries with significant commercial presence, as it plays a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurial success.

Challenges in the 21st century include increased instances of corporate fraud and governance breaches, regulatory liberalization measures in India, and the need for accountability to stakeholders. To improve accountability, the empowerment of independent directors and increased responsibilities for directors should be incorporated into Indian company law.

In conclusion, effective corporate governance is essential for creating an optimal investment climate, fostering entrepreneurial success, and maintaining a strong corporate culture. For best results, regulatory measures should be modelled after Indian corporate practices and environments, requiring board and promoters to embrace improvements in form and spirit.

Keywords: regulatory liberalization, strong corporate culture, entrepreneurial success

I. INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance is a comprehensive concept that encompasses the various procedures, traditions, regulations, and institutions that guide organizations and businesses in their actions,

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management, and oversight of their activities. The organization effectively fulfils its objectives and effectively oversees the interactions between various stakeholders, such as the board of directors and stockholders. The topic at hand also pertains to the issue of individual accountability inside an organization, namely addressing the challenge of the principal-agent dilemma through the implementation of a mechanism. Effective corporate governance is a crucial need for creating an optimal investment climate, enabling competitive firms to have a robust foothold in efficient financial markets.

Effective corporate governance is essential for countries that have a significant commercial presence since it plays a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurial success. Over the past two decades, the predominant emphasis of study in the field of finance has been on the subject of corporate governance. The fundamental issue confronting companies is the agency difficulties arising from the separation of ownership and control. This gives rise to several concerns pertaining to the effective management of corporate assets in order to serve the best interests of all stakeholders of the organization. Significant study has been conducted in the field of corporate governance, specifically focusing on the issue of agency-related problems.

II. WHAT IS CORPORATE GOVERNANCE?

The rules, policies, and procedures by which a corporation is governed are collectively referred to as "corporate governance." The goal of good corporate governance is to strike a balance between competing interests, such as those of shareholders, top management, consumers, suppliers, lenders, regulators, and the general public. To this end, corporate governance spans the gamut of management practices, including but not limited to strategic planning, internal control mechanisms, performance evaluation, and public reporting.

Community and investor relations depend on open communication about the company's corporate governance. Company leadership (executive team, board of directors) and corporate governance (committee charters, bylaws, stock ownership guidelines, articles of incorporation, etc.) are described, for example, on Apple Inc.'s investor relations site.

The vast majority of businesses actively works to maintain a high degree of corporate governance. It is not sufficient for a firm to simply be profitable for many shareholders; the

company also needs to demonstrate excellent corporate citizenship by demonstrating environmental awareness, ethical behaviour, and solid corporate governance processes. A clear set of rules and controls is the product of good corporate governance, which produces an environment in which the interests of shareholders, directors, and officers are aligned.

III. CASE STUDY

People often talk about bad company governance. In fact, this is a common reason why businesses make the news. Good corporate governance means that a company stays out of trouble. That's why you don't hear much about them. PepsiCo is a company that seems to have always used good corporate governance and often changes or adapts it. PepsiCo asked investors for feedback in six areas when writing its 2020 vote statement:

- Board composition, diversity, and refreshment, plus leadership structure
- Long-term strategy, corporate purpose, and sustainability issues
- Good governance practices and ethical corporate culture
- Human capital management
- Compensation discussion and analysis
- Shareholder and stakeholder engagement

A graphical representation of the company's current leadership structure was provided in the proxy statement the company submitted. It demonstrated a combined chair and CEO, in addition to an independent presiding director, and it established a connection between the organization's "Winning With Purpose" mission and improvements to the executive remuneration program.

IV. CHALLENGES IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Over the past decade, there has been a notable increase in instances of corporate fraud and governance breaches across the global business landscape. Consequently, there has been a corresponding surge in initiatives aimed at enhancing corporate governance procedures. India has undertaken regulatory liberalization measures to harmonize its corporate governance

standards with those observed in developed nations. However, the pursuit of effective governance and the sustainability of its outcomes remain a paramount concern for stakeholders in the present era.

Top 7 issues and challenges that affect corporate governance are stated below:

1. **Accountability to Stakeholders** - The empowerment of independent directors needs to be accompanied by increased responsibilities for directors as well as more accountability from directors. In this context, Indian company law, which was updated in 2013, specifies that directors owe duties not just towards the firm and shareholders, but also towards the employees, the community, and for the protection of the environment. Despite the fact that all directors have been assigned these general responsibilities, directors, especially independent directors, have become complacent due to a lack of enforcement action. In order to improve accountability, it could be a good idea to stipulate that the entirety of the board must be present at all general meetings. This would provide the chance for stakeholders to engage in conversation with the board and ask questions.
2. **Risk Management** - Large corporations are constantly under the watchful eye of national and international news organizations. Since the board's duty is limited to monitoring the company's operations, a risk management strategy must be developed and put into place. Here, Indian company law mandates that the board provide a statement in its report to shareholders detailing the company's approach to risk management. The independent directors are obligated to review the risk management systems of the organization. A solid risk management policy outlining fundamental concepts and methods for minimizing risks in day-to-day operations is crucial for a governance model's success.
3. **Privacy and Data Protection** - Privacy and data security are important issues for governance because they are a key part of risk management. In this digital age, every director should know the basics of internet security. CEOs can only have good control if they can work with and understand the experts in their company. The board needs to think about the risks that come with handling data and take steps to make sure that data is safe from being

misused. A fair amount of time and money must be spent by the board to make sure the goal of data safety is met.

4. **Boards approach to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)** - India is among the few nations with CSR laws. CSR committees must be formed by the board for companies meeting certain benchmarks. This committee creates a CSR policy and recommends CSR spending. Company spending must be 2% of the average net profits of the last three years. The boards of companies that fail to reach the CSR spend must explain why in their report. Last year, companies that did not comply received notifications from the ministry of corporate affairs asking for reasons why they did not spend on CSR and sometimes questioning their justifications. In these situations, the board must concentrate on CSR. Company boards should treat CSR programs as seriously as other corporate ventures.
5. **Getting the board correct** - Board and its importance as a foundation of sound corporate governance have been discussed at length elsewhere. Because of this, the law mandates appointing at least one female director in addition to a diverse mix of executive and non-executive directors. It's clear that a company's governance practices would benefit greatly from having a board that is competent, diverse, and engaged. The difficulty lies in changing business cultures to prioritize compliance "in spirit" by making governance a part of everyday practices. While many Indian businesses claim to follow the law on paper, in practice board members are still often appointed through informal channels such as "word of mouth" or referrals from other board members. In India, promoters (a term for the company's founders and controlling owners) and management often appoint close personal and family acquaintances to serve on the board. Innovative solutions are the need of the hour - for instance, grading board diversity and governance procedures and disclosing such results or utilizing performance evaluation as a minimal baseline for director appointment.
6. **Performance evaluation of directors** - Director performance evaluation is allowed in India, but the regulator suddenly noticed it. Indian capital markets regulator SEBI issued a 'Guidance Note on Board Evaluation' in January 2017. This note explained how to set goals, criteria, and evaluation methods for performance evaluation. Public performance evaluation

reports are often needed to improve governance procedures. However, appraisal is sensitive and public revelations may backfire. Negative peer review feedback may be withheld to prevent public attention. This behaviour can be avoided with independent directors evaluating performance.

7. **Independence of Directors** - The biggest change to corporate governance was meant to be the appointment of independent directors. But after 15 years, independent members haven't really made the difference that was hoped for. On the other hand, the regulator has tightened the rules many times: they have outlined fully what an independent director is, what the audit committee's job is, and so on. But most Indian marketers come up with a "tick-the-box" way to get around the rules. It's not clear how independent these independent directors are because the promoter probably hired them, and it's unlikely that they will fight for minority interests against the producer. Even with all the changes to control, the regulator is still not good enough. Maybe the focus should move to limiting the promoter's power when it comes to independent directors.

V. KEY TO OVERCOME THESE CHALLENGES

1. **Investment in Compliance Cost** - While the cost of compliance may seem high at first, it will save you a lot of money in the long run. Simplifying clear rules could help the business run more smoothly and also boost corporate governance because it will cost less to follow the rules.
2. **Strict Rules for Transparency** - Transparency is crucial to corporate governance, but there is no clear law on what to report. Clearly defined transparency requirements will simplify and improve company governance. Effective corporate governance in India might start with transparency strategy strengthening.
3. **Competence of Directors** - Directors should be honest and courageous enough to speak their minds. Business operations and financial jargon should be familiar to them. Effective corporate governance requires independent directors with company-specific skills.

4. **Regulatory Rules for Unlisted Companies** - It is imperative to extend the scope of corporate governance to encompass unlisted enterprises since this would foster a climate of robust competition and enhance the pursuit of competitive objectives. The implementation of standards and incentives is necessary for mid-sized new entrants in the capital market. Currently, there exist limited provisions for unlisted corporations that allow them to evade any consequences regarding corporate governance.

VI. CONCLUSION

Corporate governance requires complete transparency, integrity, and responsibility from the administration and board. Everywhere needs effective corporate governance in finance, taxation, banking, and law. Corporate Excellence should come after Corporate Governance. Once solid Corporate Governance is realized, the Indian Commercial Body would flourish globally. In the Indian context, the constant occurrence of forgeries since the inception of the liberalisation concept in 1991 has highlighted the necessity for corporate governance. Harshad Mehta, Ketan Parikh, UTI, Vanishing Company, and Bhansali were just a few examples of frauds that occurred. In the Indian business environment, global standards must be implemented so that, although the potential for fraud may remain, it can be minimized to an absolute minimum.

There are several benefits associated with corporate governance and ethical behaviour. The primary function of these efforts is to cultivate a positive brand image for the organization. The establishment of a brand image fosters increased fidelity, which in turn leads to heightened loyalty. This enhanced loyalty, in conjunction with a commitment to employees, subsequently cultivates a more creative workforce. Hence, for best results, regulatory measures should be modelled after Indian corporate practices and environments which requires the board and promoters to embrace improvements in form and spirit.